

S I N G L E

D8.2 Quality Control Plan

WP8, T8.1

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Technical references

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the Quality Control Plan (QCP) to be implemented and updated in the SINGLE project. This plan will ensure that the necessary protocols and tools are available within the SINGLE consortium to ensure that the work carried out in the project complies with high quality and HSE standards.

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

v	Date	Author(s)	Description
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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the Quality Control Plan (QCP) to be implemented and updated in the SINGLE project. Task 8.2 “Quality monitoring and risk assessment [M1-M36]” involving all partners has been included in SINGLE to account for this activity. The task will ensure that the work carried out in the project complies with high quality and HSE standards.

The QCP will summarize protocols for proof-reading and validating the workflow for approval of deliverables, milestones and dissemination related documents. Procedures associated to documentation control, reporting, validation, are specified. The Project Coordinator (PC) will act as a quality assurance contact to guarantee high level project deliverables.

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2. Overall layout of the QCP

The QCP will describe the following:

- Procedures for meetings
- Procedures for reviewing deliverables
- Procedures for reviewing milestones
- Procedures for reviewing dissemination activities
- Procedures for monitoring risks
- Health, safety and environment

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3. Procedures for meetings

3.1. Technical meetings

All project partners are encouraged to propose and set up technical meetings for the development of SINGLE project. The PC should be informed and invited to all technical meetings. If the meeting is organized by a task leader, the WP leader should be informed and invited as well. Minutes of technical meetings will be recorded only when deemed necessary by the PC. If the PC determines that it is necessary, the meeting organizer is responsible for recording meeting minutes.

3.2. Project progress meetings

The consortium will meet regularly to monitor the progress of the project. Approximately every six months, face-to-face meetings will be held at one of the consortium members facilities. Meeting locations rotate among consortium members, enabling to visit each member's facilities. The procedures for preparation, execution, reporting and following up of meetings is:

- Preparation: the PC in collaboration with the hosting partner will set up a date and agenda for the meeting.
- Meeting execution: go through each point set in the agenda. Define action list with responsible partners and timeline based on discussion.
- Reporting: the chairperson will produce minutes of each meeting which will be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she will send draft minutes to all members within 10 calendar days of the meeting, integrate feedback to the minutes, and save the accepted minutes in the SINGLE SharePoint.
- Follow up: the PC will communicate with Task leader(s) and WP leader(s) to follow up on action list.

3.3. General Assembly meetings

For the General Assembly meetings, the protocol is set in the Consortium Agreement of SINGLE.

The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the General Assembly at least once every six months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member.

The chairperson shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member as soon as possible and no later than 14 calendar days preceding an ordinary meeting and 7 calendar days preceding an extraordinary meeting.

The chairperson shall prepare and send each Member an agenda no later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting, or 7 calendar days before an extraordinary meeting.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members must be identified as such on the agenda.

The chairperson shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send draft minutes to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting.

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from receipt, no Party has sent an objection to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft minutes by written notice.

The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the Members, and to the Coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the minutes has been accepted.

4. Procedures for deliverables and milestones

4.1. Review of deliverables

A specific word document template has been created to be used for reporting deliverables. The deliverable will be uploaded to the participant portal site of SINGLE. Procedure for review of deliverables prior to uploading is depicted in the Table below.

Table 1: Timeline for preparation, review and submission of deliverables.

Process Stage	Time	Action	Actor
Reminder	6 weeks before due date	Reminder to lead partner and WP leader	PC
Drafting phase	4 weeks before due date	Contribution of partners identified	Lead partner
		Review by involved partners	Involved partners
	2 weeks before due date	Submission to Coordinator for quality and compliance check	Lead partner
Quality check	10 days before due date	Revision and eventual edits	Coordinator
		Revise in accordance to modifications/suggestions	Lead partner
Submission	Due date	Final approval and submission	Coordinator

4.2. Review of milestones

Milestones are project checkpoints, helping the evaluation and monitoring of project progress. WP Leaders are responsible for the timely achievement of the

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milestones as identified in the Grant Agreement (GA). The PC will monitor their progress throughout the duration of the Project. In case of potential delays, the PC will work with the responsible WP leader to develop a contingency plan.

A specific word document template for each milestone has been created to be used for continuously updating milestones and final reporting. The documents are stored on the internal SharePoint of SINGLE. Specific deliverables linked to key Milestones will be used to support the delivery of milestones. The milestones monitoring files will be updated and reviewed at least every Project progress meeting.

Once a milestone has been reached, the responsible beneficiary should inform the PC specifying the exact delivery date. The PC will then update the milestones monitoring file in SINGLE SharePoint and record the accomplishment on the Portal Continuous Reporting.

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5. Procedures related to dissemination activities

Procedure of dissemination activities in SINGLE are given in the Consortium Agreement. An illustration of the guidelines set for the dissemination activities are given below.

Figure 1: Guidelines for dissemination activities in SINGLE.

6. Procedure for identifying and monitoring risks

Risk analysis and monitoring include already identified risks of the project as set out in the DoA as well as any unforeseen events or risks detected by WP and/or Task Leaders. During the project the PC will identify the factors that are critical to the final success of the project and control these factors. If necessary, the PC will trigger the implementation of mitigation/contingency measures, propose any revision or redirection of the work plan. Periodic reports on potential risks for project implementation will be given in:

- D8.8 Periodic Risk Analysis – year 1
- D8.9 Periodic Risk Analysis – year 2
- D8.10 Periodic Risk Analysis – year 3

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7. Health, Safety and Environment (HSE)

Monitoring and ensuring a high standard of HSE is prioritised during the implementation of the SINGLE project. The following tools have been set to enforce this consideration and for monitoring purposes:

- Early identification of risks during the project building phase with proposed mitigation measures.
- Dedicated deliverable associated with the design, assembly, construction, and testing of the 10 kg H₂/day plant.
 - o D4.2 Operation protocols and safety assessments, including HAZOP
 - o D8.8 Periodic Risk Analysis – Year 1
 - o D8.9 Periodic Risk Analysis – Year 2
 - o D8.10 Periodic Risk Analysis -Year 3
- The project will through T7.5 “Standardization activities” collect and provide information and comply with relevant EU legislative and standard frameworks.

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